

FORMATION OF MODELING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This thesis is devoted to the study of the theoretical and practical foundations of the formation of modeling skills in elementary school students. The importance of modeling in the educational process, its role in the development of students' creative thinking and problem-solving skills is analyzed. The article also describes methods and pedagogical approaches aimed at developing modeling skills. Taking into account the age characteristics of students, recommendations are given to increase the effectiveness of teaching modeling.

Key words: Primary class, modeling, creative thinking, educational technologies, pedagogical methods, practical skills, educational process, didactic materials, primary education.

Introduction.

Today, the development of creative and intellectual abilities of students in primary education is one of the urgent pedagogical issues. Based on this, modeling in the educational process serves not only to apply theoretical knowledge to practice, but also to form students' skills such as problem analysis, logical thinking and creative approach.

Through modeling technology, elementary school students will have the opportunity to understand various processes and express them based on their own models. This helps to master the educational content in depth and creates an important foundation for acquiring knowledge in the future.

This article is devoted to the study of the pedagogical and methodical foundations of the formation of modeling skills in elementary school students, and is aimed at determining the role and importance of this process in increasing the effectiveness of education. The role of modeling in modern education, the processes of its organization and effective methods are analyzed in the article.

Literature review: The study of scientific and literary sources dedicated to the formation of modeling skills shows that this field is of great importance in education and has been widely researched both theoretically and practically. In pedagogical literature, modeling technology is considered as an important part

of the educational process, and its role in the development of students' thinking is emphasized.

The theoretical foundations of the modeling concept have been studied by many scientists. A.N. Leontev[2] and L.S. In Vygotsky's[1] psychological research, special attention was paid to the development of students' problem-solving abilities through modeling. Their research highlights the importance of modeling in the formation of students' logical and creative thinking.

Among the scientific works on the modeling process in primary education, V.V. Davydov[3] and D.B. Elkonin's activity-based approaches are important. They reasoned that the activity approach can increase the effectiveness of modeling methods in the development of students' logical thinking.

Modern studies, including P.M. Erdnieva and I.Yu. Zybycheva[4] in the works of scientists such as the methods of modeling with the help of information technologies were studied. Their research emphasized the effectiveness of developing modeling skills through the use of electronic tools, visual programs, and educational projects.

The analysis of the literature shows that the integration of modeling into the educational process serves to develop students' creative and practical skills. At the same time, the development and improvement of modeling methods and technologies has not lost its relevance even now, and is recognized as the main tool in the development of the cognitive activity of students in primary education.

Discussion: The process of forming modeling skills among elementary school students plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. The results of the research show that modeling technology is one of the main tools for developing students' creative and critical thinking. This process strengthens students' observation, problem-solving skills, and practical application of theoretical knowledge.

As it was determined during the research, the inclusion of modeling in the educational process helps students to understand knowledge more deeply. Students are more interested in understanding various processes and expressing them through modeling. Especially through the models used in practical activities, the stability of knowledge increases and students' self-assessment skills develop.

Studies have shown that for the effective implementation of modeling, it is important to create problem situations in the educational process, to give students the opportunity to make independent decisions, and also to enrich

educational materials with didactic tools. Lessons organized on the basis of the activity approach showed positive results in the development of modeling skills.

Based on the results of the discussion, it was determined that the use of modeling methods in the educational process can increase the activity of not only elementary school students, but also students of other levels. At the same time, technological approaches (electronic platforms and interactive tools) increase efficiency in the organization of modeling.

During the discussion, modeling was accepted as an integral part of primary education. This approach not only enriches students' theoretical and practical knowledge, but also helps them develop self-development, creative approach, and problem-solving skills. Therefore, the integration of modeling into the educational process on a large scale is an urgent task of modern pedagogical activity.

Conclusion.

Formation of modeling skills in primary school students is an important tool for improving educational efficiency as an innovative approach to the educational process. The results revealed during the study showed the following: The role of modeling in education: Modeling technology serves to develop students' logical thinking, creative approach, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge to practice.

Effectiveness of pedagogical approaches: An activity-based approach and the organization of problem situations give high results in the formation of modeling skills. The development of educational content, taking into account the age characteristics of students, increases efficiency. Integrating modern information technologies into the modeling process encourages students to gain deeper knowledge of the subject. Organization of modeling lessons through interactive tools and visual materials significantly increases the level of students' mastery. In order to introduce modeling into the educational process on a large scale, it is necessary to develop special methodical manuals for pedagogues, to create an environment equipped with modern tools and technologies.

In short, the formation of modeling skills is an effective method of all-round development of students not only in primary education, but also in other educational stages. This process is crucial in the formation of students' independent thinking, problem solving and creative approach.

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